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PILOT 2021
2026

DELIVERABLE REPORT

WP17 JA7 – Communication and Dissemination

D17.3

NFFA Communication Toolkit

Due date

M6

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NEP

PROJECT TITLE

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Dr. Flavio Carsughi (FZJ)

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NFFA Communication Toolkit

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

This deliverable describes the concept and development of the project's visual identity and materials for the NFFA Communication Toolkit. This work is related to WP7 and its Task 17.1 and supports all communication activities of the NFFA-Europe Pilot project.

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NATURE

R – Report

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- P - Public
- PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify)
- RE - Restricted to a group (Specify)
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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PREMISE

This document outlines the development of the communication toolkit in support of NFFA Europe Pilot communication activities. A series of different materials have been produced to communicate effectively with target audiences, to support stakeholder-engagement, to promote the project among established and potentially new users and raise awareness about NFFA-Europe infrastructures in general and in particular about the new research opportunities offered thanks to NFFA-Europe Pilot.

The messages transmitted in the communication toolkit are based on the following distinction introduced in deliverable 17.1. "Terms of Reference of the Communication Plan":

- NFFA (Nanoscience foundries and fine analysis) is an innovative research model for advanced nanofabrication and characterization of nanostructures.
- NFFA-Europe is a distributed, interoperable research infrastructure, implementing the NFFA model Europe-wide and offering its users the widest possible range of tools to carry out research at the nanoscale.
- NFFA-Europe Pilot is the new project financed by the European Commission offering yet more advanced facilities specialized on growth, nano-lithography, nano-characterization, theory and simulation, resting on three fundamental pillars:
 - offering the facilities of the infrastructure free of charge to European and international users
 - developing new services to improve interoperability
 - developing new techniques to improve the offer

The material produced highlights in particular the following aspects of the NFFA-Europe Pilot:

- NFFA-Europe Infrastructure offers now an expanded catalogue with new techniques.
- A new installation "From Nano to Micro/Macro" is among the new offer, providing users with the possibility to carry out research on the micro/macro level as well.
- Access to the NFFA-Europe research infrastructure is for free thanks to the NFFA-Europe Pilot project.
- The new NFFA-Europe Pilot workplan aims to develop a new model of a distributed research infrastructure based on sustainability, integration and interoperability.

This deliverable describes the development of the communication toolkit including the updated NFFA-Europe and the resulting NFFA-Europe PILOT visual identity. The visual identity is the cornerstone of all material produced and runs like a red line through the entire design, and includes the logo, the word templates and the corporate presentation, used to present the NFFA-Europe project at conferences. In addition, the communication toolkit contains the following materials:

- leaflet/flyer
- a browsable booklet/brochure optimized for PC reading and desktop printing
- three A1 posters
- a roll up

Last but not least, conference booths will be prepared ad-hoc according to the target of the conference and the shape and size of the booth.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

Visual identity

The visual identity for the new NFFA-Europe PILOT project is the result of a continuous evolution of the visual identity developed for the previous H2020 project NFFA-Europe (1/9/2015 to 28/2/2021).

Rather than developing an entirely new visual identity we have decided to take advantage of the already existing strong identity of the NFFA brand, while expressing the particularity of PILOT. In so doing and to make sure the distinct concepts would be expressed clearly through the logo, we needed to slightly adapt the earlier NFFA-Europe logo.

In the following subchapter the development of the PILOT logo evolving from the NFFA brand will be explained in more detail:

Logo

1. The NFFA (Nanoscience foundries and fine analysis) logo represents the research model for advanced nanofabrication and characterization of nanostructures.

Figure 1: NFFA logo

2. The NFFA-Europe logo represents a new model of a distributed research infrastructure based on integration, interoperability and sustainability that outlives individual projects. To express that new concept and to give weight to the longevity of the structure, the term “research infrastructure” was added to the logo underneath.

Figure 2: NFFA-Europe Research Infrastructure logo

3. The NFFA-Europe Pilot logo represents the new project financed by the European Commission, thanks to which the new model as described above can be materialized and the research offer can be delivered free of charge to users whose research plan has been approved.

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Figure 3: NFFA-Europe PILOT logo

The idea behind the PILOT logo is to express that logical evolution of PILOT from earlier NFFA projects, while also showing its distinctiveness. The connection to NFFA is expressed through the coupling of the NFFA symbol and wordmark with the PILOT wordmark in the logo. We have consciously avoided creating a new symbol for PILOT, so as to avoid confusion among users. The distinctiveness of PILOT is expressed through its wordmark with PILOT written in orange and all in capital letters. Furthermore, it clearly indicates the timeframe of the project as running from 2021 to 2026. The entire portfolio of communication materials, which will be explained further down in this document) contains a strong component of the colour orange, making particular reference to PILOT.

Templates

Templates complying with the graphical character of the project have been created and made available to all partners.

Word templates

Word templates have been developed for official documents (e.g. headed letters, deliverables, progress reports, others). Using these templates, partners will have full control over the content while ensuring the coherence of the visuals.

Figure 4: word templates

PowerPoint templates

PowerPoint templates were developed for partners to be used for presentations at project meetings and especially during external meetings or conferences.

Figure 5: power point templates

Corporate presentation

A corporate presentation, explaining the basic concepts of NFFA-Europe PILOT, has been created for use by all partners. It includes an overview of all the techniques offered, the partners involved, how to gain access to the infrastructure and some simple statistics related to the characteristics of research proposals received during the past years.

Figure 6: corporate presentation

Communication Material

Promoscience developed the first material of the communication toolkit including:

- leaflet/flyer
- a browsable booklet/brochure optimized for PC reading and desktop printing
- three A1 posters
- a roll-up

Further material, depending on the partners needs may be produced additionally during the project lifetime. Possibly a final booklet containing a description of the major project outputs may be designed as well.

All promotional material has been developed on the base of the key messages laid out in the premise of this document. The main slogan "for your project at the nano- & the microscale" lets readers immediately understand what this material is about, but also creates curiosity, inviting them to learn more. All the material makes reference to the EU funds and prompts the reader to act upon it by visiting the webpage via url or QR code.

Leaflet

The developed leaflet is a 4-page flyer in A4 format, folded twice. It will be printed and distributed at project and external events, conferences and fairs so as to gain visibility among the general public and stakeholders.

at the nano- & the microscale

HOW TO APPLY

- 1 BROWSE & CHOOSE**
Visit www.nffa.eu, browse the offer & select the tools you need
- 2 SUBMIT YOUR PROPOSAL**
on our single-entry point
- 3 HAVE IT EVALUATED**
& ranked by an international peer-review panel
- 4 GET FREE ACCESS**
and receive a contribution for travel & subsistence costs

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COORDINATOR: CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

PARTNERS: CEA Commissariat à l'Énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives / CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique / CSIC Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas / DESY Sinfund Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY / ELETTRA* Centro Sincrotrone Trieste / EPFL Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne / ESRF Installation Européenne de Rayonnement Synchrotron / EXACT Lab srl / FORTH Foundation for Research and Technology / Helmholtz-Zentrum für Materialforschung GmbH / ICN2 Fundació Institut Català de Nanociència i Nanotecnologia / INL International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory / JRC Joint Research Centre / KIT Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie / LU Lunds Universitet / Promoscience srl / PRIAS* Parc de Recerca iMB / PSI Paul Scherrer Institute / SOLEIL* Soleil Synchrotron / TUG Technische Universität Graz / TUM Technische Universität München / UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona / UMIL Università degli Studi di Milano / UNG Università v Novi Gorici

NFFA-Europe branding by Promoscience; Photo Courtesy (in order of appearance): P. Gilber - ESRF; M. Tormen - CNR-IOM; P. Organi - CNR-IOM; SA - Argonne National Laboratory; Max Planck working group, Hamburg; DESY

for your project

The widest range of tools for research at the nano- & the microscale

Figure 7: outer side of the leaflet

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PILOT 2021 2026

Thanks to the support of the European Union, a new pilot model of sustainable research is currently being developed, resting on the following pillars:

- Optimal integration
- Interoperability
- A new generation of researchers
- Long-term sustainability

FREE OF CHARGE ACCESS FOR ACADEMIA AND INDUSTRY

	ELECTRONIC & CHEMICAL, MAGNETIC CHARACTERIZATION <small>Including nanolab-based tools and techniques</small>		
	FROM NANO TO MICRO/MACRO <small>Pool of techniques from the nano-, micro- up to the macroscale</small>		
	THEORY & SIMULATION <small>Atomistic computer modelling of materials</small>		

Figure 8: inner side of the leaflet

Booklet

The NFFA-Europe PILOT booklet consists of a 16-page long brochure describing in more detail the services offered and how to gain access. Particular focus has been placed on the new features related to NFFA-Europe PILOT. The booklet is designed for printing in the format 18 x 18 centimetres, but is also browsable and optimized for PC reading and easy desktop printing.

Figure 9: cover page and mock-up of the booklet

Figure 10: inner pages of the booklet

Posters

Three different A1 posters at varying degrees of detail have been created to promote NFFA-Europe PILOT at conferences, talks and events. All of them point to the new features related to NFFA-Europe PILOT and highlight the free of charge access for approved users.

Figure 11: NFFA-Europe PILOT posters

Roll-Up

The project roll-up has been developed for display at partner institutions, events, conferences, talks, etc. It introduces the topic with the slogan “for your project at the nano- & the microscale”, displays the six techniques and explains how to get access.

Figure 12: NFFA-Europe PILOT posters

